

What That Means, in Physics, the Advice
Let's read the Classics? The case of Louis de
Broglie's *Introduction to Wave Mechanics*.

Stelios Tsekouras*

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*2nd Lyceum of Argyroupolis-"G. Seferis".

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1 Introduction.

2 Louis de Broglie (1892-1987).

M. de Broglie, so I believe, disliked the probability interpretation of wave mechanics as much as I did.

Erwin Schrödinger in *The Meaning of Wave Mechanics*, [7].

We have abundant evidence and testimony that Louis de Broglie deeply cared about the foundations, the meaning, and our understanding of quantum theory in general and of wave mechanics in particular. So, too, did Erwin Schrödinger, along with Einstein, Bohr, Dirac, and Heisenberg. For de Broglie and Schrödinger this preoccupation meant not simply the acceptance of a novel set of rules, but a constant struggle and a search for complete clarity about the way in which the new theory fits into the great classical traditions of an objective physical world view. We may call this a striving for "physical rigor," rigor in reasoning, or intellectual rigor. There is not only mathematical rigor inside an axiomatic system with which everybody agrees, but there is, and there should be, rigor also in our concepts and methods. To this kind of rigor belongs the unity, the economy and simplicity, and the consistency of physical theories; naturally along with as complete and as clear an understanding of phenomena as possible. No loose ends, no proliferation of poorly used, and no handwaiving arguments can be tolerated. Unfortunately this kind of rigor seems to be missing in today's forefront of fundamental physical theories, viz., particle or high-energy physics. This branch of physics should go hand in hand with, in fact ought to be the testing ground for, the elucidation of the two most important theories of this century, relativity and quantum theory. Instead, particle physics seems to have separated itself from the rest of physics, developed its own jargon and logic, and does not appear

to worry about its foundations. This turn of events has its origin, I believe, in the rapid acceptance and success of the rules of quantum theory without an accompanying full understanding of these rules. Which brings us back to Louis de Broglie.

From the Foreword by A.O. Barut to *Heisenberg's Uncertainties and the Probabilistic Interpretation of Wave Mechanics*, by Louis de Broglie, [5].

Louis de Broglie is one of the fathers of Quantum Mechanics. Despite that honor he has gained much less reputation than the others and one can reasonably think that this fact is principally due to his determined resistance, deeply rooted in scientific grounds and not solely in philosophical ones, to the dominant 'Copenhagen' interpretation of Quantum Mechanics. In [4], page 13, de Broglie writes that: " *Au Conseil Solvay qui eut lieu a Bruxelles en Octobre 1927, je fus presque seul a proposer des idées différentes des celles de Pauli, Heisenberg et Dirac. Seuls Einstein et Lorentz, sans approuver entièrement mes conceptions, refusèrent d'admettre celles de l'École de Copenhague... Chargé en 1928 d'un enseignement de Physique théorique a la Faculté des Sciences de Paris, je me suis résigné, non sans quelques réticences comme cela se voit encore dans le premier de mes cours, a enseigner ce qui était devenu la doctrine officielle et je l'ai fait pendant plus de vingt ans.*" On the other hand it is not exaggerated to say that the academia (or, at least, a large part of it) continued (even after the end of the 2nd World War) to be hostile towards his ideas and this fact was certainly influenced by the dominant intellectual clima during the Cold War. Werner Heisenberg in his well-known booklet: *The Physical Principles of the Quantum Theory*, mentions de Broglie only to say that: " *We first encounter attempts to develop three dimensional wave theories that could be readily visualised (Maxwell and de Broglie waves)*" (page 47 of [18]). Some pages after this mention of de Broglie's name Heisenberg says the following: " *The classical wave theory is that of de Broglie waves for matter and for electromagnetic waves of radiation*" (page 157 of [18]). Those two remarks give the false impression that, in reality, de Broglie's work had nothing to do with Quantum Mechanics. The least I can say is that this Heisenberg's approach of de Broglie's contributions does not clarify the essence of de Broglie's work. The notorious physicist and Nobel Prize winner Murray Gell-Mann does not make even the slightest mention of de Broglie in [23], a book written in 1995!! He nevertheless informs us, in page 170 of [23], that David Bohm told him, in 1951, that '*as a Marx-*

ist he had had difficulty believing in Quantum Mechanics. (Marxists tend to prefer their theories to be fully deterministic.)'. Since everyone knows that David Bohm was a close collaborator of de Broglie, it is easy to understand that ridiculizing Bohm the notorious scientist attacked de Broglie. Of course this kind of discussion is not a scientific one! Leonard I. Schiff, the writer of a well-known textbook, [19], which was used by generations of physicists doesn't mention even de Broglie's name, although in 1968 (date of publication of the third edition of this book) Louis de Broglie was still an active researcher!!! It would be unacceptable not to mention some eminent physicists, Asim Orhan Barut (1926-1994), Mendel Sachs (1927-2012), John Stewart Bell (1928-1990), Gian-Carlo Ghirardi (1935-2018) among them, who had a rather positive approach to Louis de Broglie's scientific ideas! At last but not at least, the reader has to constantly bear in mind the fact that Louis de Broglie is not doing Philosophy of Physics¹. He is doing Physics!

Nowadays we acknowledge a profound crisis in modern physics. This crisis insects many thinkers to revisit and question the foundations of Quantum Mechanics thus proceeding to a revival of de Broglie's work. On the other hand revisiting the foundations of Physics is not an easy task. The teacher willing to understand the elements of the Quantum Mechanical Revolution² cannot work with the extremely dense, full of technicalities papers of the forefront research. He needs, instead, a scientifically credible guide to initiate and sustain the gradual development of his thoughts. Let me point to the fact that the second property (to sustain) is much more interesting than the first one (to initiate). Because only the success of such a development can ameliorate the efficiency of his teaching activity.

The present article is the result of a personal investigation whose outcome was to convince me that THE INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY OF WAVE MECHANICS [1] is an easy to find (in electronic form) and suitable for such a work book.

Who embarks to such a painfull duty is confronted to two major difficulties:

1. If he tries to rest on the many textbooks of Quantum Mechanics he runs

¹Although he has written many excellent texts concerning the Philosophy of Physics.

²Needless to say that our attention has to be directed to the concatenation of ideas and not to the memorization of the words used. Georges Lochak in his Préface of [3] rightly points the fact that Louis de Broglie changed his opinion between 1936 and 1973. In 1936 wave mechanics was for him a *couronnement* (coronation) but in 1973 it was a *révolution* (revolution).

the danger to unconsciously follow the errors made by the authors of those textbooks in their understandable tendency to be conformal with the curriculum. Needless to say that I do not mean that these authors are incompetent but only that there exist a sharp tension between the teaching necessities of the instructor, the understanding necessities of the student and the logic of the curriculum!

2. If he tries to inspire himself from the so called science popularization books he faces the time-consuming task of choosing the more appropriate sources. Those books offer a huge number of references for which it is not easy to say in advance which of them are good and which are bad. Yet most of the modern books have a rather limited audience and pay little attention to the essential needs of the general reader.

3 The Structure of *The Introduction to the Study of Wave Mechanics*, [1].

3.1 The Chapters and their paragraphs.

Mais cette idée je la précise en disant que la particule doit être le siège d'un mouvement périodique et *qu'elle doit se déplacer dans son onde de façon à rester en phase avec elle*, ce qui détermine son mouvement dans l'onde. Ce raisonnement qui est exposé dans le premier chapitre de ma thèse et qui avait beaucoup frappé Einstein, paraît, chose bien surprenante, être complètement ignoré des physiciens quantistes actuels.

In page 12 of [4].

The Contents of [1] are included in the General Introduction followed by nineteen Chapters. Louis de Broglie points out that the General Introduction *"is the reproduction of a communication made by the author at the meeting of the British Association for the Advancement of Science held in Glasgow in September, 1928."*

If we look closer, as we will soon do, at the structure of the above mentioned chapters it is easy to discern a striking difference between de Broglie's method of presentation of Quantum Mechanics and the one now prevailing. The great physicist does not begin his presentation by pointing either

to the multiple computational methods of the subject, either to a spectacular phenomenon having no operational place inside the overall structure of his book. He insists, instead, on the concatenation of the fundamental physical ideas thus giving a very inspiring (and formatting!) overview of the subject. Inspiring as it constantly fuels the curiosity of the reader and formatting as it helps him understand the above mentioned concatenation before the mathematical technicalities. In order to achieve the ability to produce such vivid presentations Louis de Broglie had worked hardly for many years. In the short but excellent *Avant-propos*³ of his book *RÉCHERCHES D'UN DÉMI-SIÈCLE*, [4], he writes: ” *Attaché, en dehors de mes heures de service, au laboratoire du poste, j’ai appris que la physique ne consiste pas à écrire des équations, mais à comprendre d’une façon concrète le déroulement des phénomènes. C’est mon passage au poste de la Tour Eiffel qui m’a aussi appris à être toujours extrêmement exact et précis dans l’exécution de toutes mes tâches.*”

The Chapters are:

- Chapter I: THE OLD SYSTEMS OF MECHANICS OF A PARTICLE.
This chapter contains six paragraphs:

1. Hamilton’s Principle.
2. The Equations of Lagrange.
3. The Lagrangian Function. Momentum and Energy.
4. Another form of Hamilton’s Principle. The Principle of Maupertuis.
5. The Hamiltonian Canonical Equations.
6. Contact Transformations.

Louis de Broglie considers that the Old Systems of Mechanics of a Particle are the Classical or Newtonian one and the Relativistic Mechanics of Einstein. He remarks:” *The essential point is that all the formulae of Newtonian Mechanics can be deduced from the Mechanics of Einstein by supposing that the velocity of light in empty space is infinitely great; in other words, the classical formulae are always obtained from the relativistic formulae by a development in a series in powers of v/c and by omitting the terms of higher orders.* (Page 11 of [1].) Further

³Which is rather a concise autobiography!

on he makes another pertinent remark:” *Up to this point our dynamical theory has remained, as it were, a blank form, since we have not stated the form of the function L in the It is just at this point that the mechanics of Newton and Einstein diverge in that the choice of L is different.* (Page 13 of [1].) In pages 15 to 16 of [1], he introduces the concept of Energy. He begins paragraph 4 (page 17 of [1]) pointing out that:” *We proceed now to show that it is possible to give to Hamilton’s integral of action the form of an integral along a curve.*

- Chapter II: THE THEORY OF JACOBI. This chapter contains six paragraphs:
 1. The equation of Jacobi.
 2. Hamilton’s Integral and Jacobi’s Function.
 3. The Reduced Function of Jacobi.
 4. Different Forms of Jacobi’s Equation.
 5. Jacobi’s Function in the case of Uniform Rectilinear Motion.
 6. Jacobi’s Function in a Uniform Constant Field.
- Chapter III: THE CONCEPTIONS UNDERLYING WAVE MECHANICS. This chapter contains five paragraphs:
 1. The point of Departure.
 2. An alternative Method of Obtaining the Preceding Results.
 3. Refractive Index. Fundamental Theorem on the Group-Velocity of the ψ -waves.
 4. Relations between Wave and Mechanical Quantities.
 5. The Principle of Least Action and Fermat’s Principle.
- Chapter IV: GENERAL REMARKS ON WAVE PROPAGATION. This chapter contains seven paragraphs:
 1. The Propagation of Waves in a Permanent Homogeneous Medium.
 2. Dispersion.
 3. Trains and Groups of Waves.
 4. Propagation in a Permanent Heterogeneous Medium.

5. Construction of Wave Envelopes and Fermat's Principle.
 6. Wave Groups in a Permanent Heterogeneous Medium.
 7. Propagation of Waves in a Non-Permanent Medium.
- Chapter V: THE EQUATIONS OF PROPAGATION OF THE WAVE ASSOCIATED WITH A PARTICLE. This chapter contains five paragraphs:
 1. The Criterion for the Choice of the Equations of Propagation.
 2. The Wave Equation in the Absence of a Field of Force.
 3. The Wave Equation in a Constant Field of Force.
 4. The Wave Equation in Variable Fields of Force.
 5. A Device for Finding Equation 38.
 - Chapter VI: CLASSICAL MECHANICS AND WAVE MECHANICS. This chapter contains four paragraphs:
 1. The Meaning of Amplitude in Classical Mechanics.
 2. The Probability of Occurrence.
 3. Concrete Examples.
 4. Summary of the Chapter.
 - Chapter VII: THE PRINCIPLE OF INTERFERENCE AND THE DIFFRACTION OF ELECTRONS BY CRYSTALS. This chapter contains four paragraphs:
 1. The Principle of Interference.
 2. The Diffraction of Electrons.
 3. Preliminaries to the Study of G.P.Thomson's Experiments.
 4. Experiments of G.P.Thomson.
 - Chapter VIII: THE PRINCIPLE OF INTERFERENCE AND THE SCATTERING OF CHARGED PARTICLES BY FIXED CENTRE. This chapter contains two paragraphs:
 1. The Scattering of Charged Particles According to Classical Mechanics.

2. The Calculation by Means of Wave Mechanics.
- Chapter IX: THE MOTION OF THE PROBABILITY WAVE IN THE NEW MECHANICS. This chapter contains five paragraphs:
 1. The Probabilty Cloud.
 2. Equations of Motion of the Probability Elements.
 3. The Theorem of Ehrenfest.
 4. Calculation of the Functions ϕ and α .
 5. The Pilot Wave Theory.
 - Chapter X: THE WAVE MECHANICS OF LIGHT QUANTA. This chapter contains six paragraphs:
 1. Photons and their Associated Waves.
 2. The Probability Cloud Associated with a Photon.
 3. Interpretation of Interference Phenomena.
 4. The Interference of Light in the Neighbourhood of a Perfectly Reflecting Plane Mirror.
 5. The Interference of Light in the Neighbourhood of an Imperfectly Reflecting Plane Mirror.
 6. The Superposition of Two Plane Monochromatic Waves.
 - Chapter XI: THE THEORY OF BOHR AND HEISENBERG. This chapter contains six paragraphs:
 1. The Principle of Spectral Distribution.
 2. The Theory of Bohr and Heisenberg. The Uncertainty Relations.
 3. The Meaning of the Wave in the Theory of Bohr and Heisenberg.
 4. Agreement with the Old Dynamics.
 5. Einstein's Objection. Is the Particle non-Localisable or not-Localised?
 6. Conclusion.
 - Chapter XII: THE POSSIBILITY OF MEASUREMENT AND HEISENBERG'S RELATIONS. This chapter contains five paragraphs:

1. Methods of Measurement and Heisenberg's Relations.
 2. Heisenberg's Microscope.
 3. Measurement of the Velocity of an Electron by Means of the Doppler Effect.
 4. The Passage of a Particle through a Diaphragm.
 5. A Note on the Measurement of Velocity.
- Chapter XIII: THE PROPAGATION OF A TRAIN OF ψ -WAVES IN THE ABSENCE OF A FIELD OF FORCE AND IN A UNIFORM FIELD. This chapter contains five paragraphs:
 1. Rigorous Solution of the Equation of Propagation in the Absence of a Field of Force.
 2. The Calculations Applied to a Special Case (Darwin).
 3. The Measurement of Velocity by Two Successive Observations.
 4. Rigorous Solution of the Propagation of a ψ -Wave-train in a Uniform Constant Field of Force.
 5. Development of the Calculations in a Special Case.
 - Chapter XIV: WAVE MECHANICS OF SYSTEMS OF PARTICLES. This chapter contains four paragraphs:
 1. Summary of the Principles of the Old Dynamics of Systems.
 2. Transition from the Old to the New Dynamics of Systems.
 3. Mathematical Results.
 4. The Wave Equation in Generalised Space.
 - Chapter XV: THE INTERPRETATION OF THE WAVE ASSOCIATED WITH THE MOTION OF A SYSTEM. This chapter contains five paragraphs:
 1. The Approximation of Geometrical Optics.
 2. The General Case. Motion of Probability.
 3. Ehrenfest's theorem.
 4. The Explanation of Bohr and Heisenberg.

5. Concluding Remark.
- Chapter XVI: THE OLD QUANTUM THEORY AND THE STABILITY OF PERIODIC MOTION. This chapter contains six paragraphs.
 1. Early Examples of Quantisation in Periodic Motion.
 2. The Wilson-Sommerfeld Conditions.
 3. Einstein's Statement of the Quantum Conditions.
 4. Quantisation of Keplerian Motion.
 5. Degeneration.
 6. The Insufficiency of the Old Quantum Theory.
 - Chapter XVII: THE STABILITY OF QUANTIZED MOTION FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF WAVE MECHANICS. This chapter contains four paragraphs.
 1. Meaning of Quantisation in Wave Mechanics.
 2. Simple Examples of Characteristic Vibrations. Vibrating Strings and Membranes.
 3. A Study of the General Case of Equation (9).
 4. The Quantisation of Systems of Particles.
 - Chapter XVIII: SOME EXAMPLES OF QUANTISATION. This chapter contains four paragraphs:
 1. The Plane Rotator.
 2. The Rotator with a Free Axis.
 3. The Harmonic Oscillator.
 4. The Hydrogen Atom.
 - Chapter XIX: THE MEANING OF THE ψ -WAVES OF QUANTISED SYSTEMS. This chapter contains three paragraphs:
 1. Application of General Principles to Quantised Systems.
 2. The Influence of Perturbations on a Quantised System.
 3. The Probability Cloud and the Heisenberg Matrices.

3.2 Interesting Remarks.

The following de Broglie's remarks can help the reader orientate himself inside this difficult but rewarding book.

- *The point of departure in wave mechanics was the wish always to associate the idea of a particle with that of periodicity in such a way as to bind inseparably the idea of the motion of a particle with that of wave propagation. We shall first examine the simplest case, that of a corpuscle moving freely outside any field of force, and we shall see that the connection to be established between wave and particle is then in some measure imposed by the fundamental principles of relativity. We remind ourselves in the first place that a Galilean system of axes is a rectangular system at rest or in uniform rectilinear motion with respect to the fixed stars ; it is for systems of this kind that the equations of dynamics are valid. The principle of inertia, which is of the nature of a definition in disguise, teaches that if a particle is subject to no forces it is necessarily at rest or in uniform rectilinear motion in a Galilean system. Of the infinite number of Galilean systems let us consider two in particular. The first with respect to which the particle possesses the velocity $v(= \beta c)$ is so oriented that the particle describes the axis of z . The second, called the " proper system " of the particle, moves with respect to the first with the velocity v in magnitude and direction, and its z axis slides over that of the first system. (Page 39 of [1].)*

In the book UNDERSTANDING QUANTUM MECHANICS-A User's Manual, [8](page 39), I found the following presentation of the same subject:

Nonetheless, de Broglie proposed that equations $E = h\nu$ and $p = h/\lambda$ be used for material particles as well as photons. Thus, for electrons, atoms, photons and all other quantum particles, the energy and momentum are related to the frequency and wavelength by those equations. I cannot understand how a proposal becomes so easily a scientific fact. As the de Broglie's quote testifies, he proved his proposal, but modern textbooks don't mention this fact!! And inside de Broglie's proof there is much interesting Physics.

- *Let us place ourselves in the system of reference (x_0, y_0, z_0) which is bound to the particle. Since it is our aim to associate a wave with*

the particle, it is quite natural to suppose that this wave has the form of a stationary wave in the proper system, that is to say, that its mathematical expression depends only on the time through a factor $\cos 2\pi\nu_0(t_0 - \tau_0)$, and we can place $\tau_0 = 0$, since this depends only upon a convenient choice of the origin in time. We shall describe the constant ν_0 by the term "proper frequency" of the particle.(Page 40 of [1].)

- *The phase velocity of the wave associated with the particle is inversely proportional to the velocity of the particle itself ; it is infinite in the proper system where the particle velocity is zero.* (Page 41 of [1].)
- Concerning paragraph 3 of Chapter III the Reader can refer to the relevant sections of [21] and [22]. Paragraphs 4 and 5, are very formative as they give a global view of the problem. To refresh his memory with Plane Waves in Conducting Media he can look at [22] (pages 183-188.)
- ... *In a stroke of genius, he⁴ noted⁵ that Planck's constant h represented a quantum of action, and that the familiar quantum of energy $h\nu$ was only an indirect result of quantizing the action.* (Page v of Léon Brillouin's [20].)
- Chapter IV is fundamental. Specially, paragraph 3 (Trains and Groups of Waves) is pedagogic. If the reader wants to be convinced about that, he can compare de Broglie's presentation with Schiff's, [19] pages 14-17. One has to pay due attention to de Broglie's insistence to the Fermat's Principle (Chapters III and IV) not mentioned by Schiff [19].

4 The Prerequisites: Mechanics, Electromagnetism and Relativity.

It is impossible to understand Quantum Mechanics if one doesn't have a solid working knowledge of Electromagnetism and of Relativity theory. This is a fact. Louis de Broglie acknowledged this fact and based all his analyses on the works of his predecessors Fresnel, Maxwell, Lorentz, Poincaré, Planck, Einstein and others. Yet, if someone tries to follow the traces of

⁴Arnold Sommerfeld.

⁵1911.

those famous scientists he experiences a difficulty which becomes larger and larger as he approaches the state of the present knowledge. If someone looks more closely at Electromagnetism, whose development resulted in the birth of Relativity theory, he understands that time spent during the teaching and the subsequent assimilation of his laws is, indeed, of the utmost importance. It is, of course, possible to condensate Electromagnetism in some formulas and in some mathematical techniques⁶ but this is useless. The student cannot assimilate ideas, concepts and techniques that have never been appropriately taught to him, patiently discussed with him, worked by him. On the other hand it is astonishing what the great physicists's texts tell to us. Unfortunately, either we don't pay the due attention to them, either their extremely dense style intimidates us. So let's chose some cornerstones of Modern Physics and let's try to struggle with them.

4.1 Henri Poincaré's (1900) article: Relations entre la Physique Expérimentale et la Physique Mathématique,[16] (pages 1-29).

Experiment is the sole source of truth. It alone can teach us something new; it alone can give us certainty. These are two points that cannot be questioned. But then, if experiment is everything, what place is left for mathematical physics? What can experimental physics do with such an auxiliary - an auxiliary, moreover, which seems useless, and even may be dangerous ?

However, mathematical physics exists. It has rendered undeniable service, and that is a fact which has to be explained., [11] (page 140).

In this article Poincaré proves his remarkable ability to grasp the essence of Physics and to transform it into a powerful thinking tool for the prospective and patient readers of it. Going against the current he succeeds to articulate a scientific as well as a didactic strategy which analyses the foundations of Modern Physics. Beginning with the simplest truths he manages (in the end) to obtain profound and durable results, thus gradually changing his readers mind. Initially the reader feels that a somehow mysterious force lies

⁶This is, indeed, the strategy of modern textbooks.

behind the masters words. Then he gradually acknowledges that Poincaré's understanding of Physics is really deep.

But in nowadays scientific activity, in research and in teaching alike, we realise that the truths presented by Poincaré in this article are not governing the actions and the thoughts of the majority of researchers and of teachers. Both have succumbed to the dominant ideas, both refuse to think differently from the *mainstream*, both consider that the only worthwhile work is that consisting in doing the calculations. For all these reasons it is urgent to restudy that article. Such a study could convince us that the scientific development is not measured by the rising of the profits of big companies but, rather, by the amelioration of our own thinking ability.

When a physicist finds a contradiction between two theories which are equally dear to him, he sometimes says: "Let us not be troubled, but let us hold fast to the two ends of the chain, lest we lose the intermediate links." This argument of the embarrassed theologian would be ridiculous if we were to attribute to physical theories the interpretation given them by the man of the world. In case of contradiction one of them at least should be considered false. But this is no longer the case if we only seek in them what should be sought. It is quite possible that they both express true relations, and that the contradictions only exist in the images we have formed to ourselves of reality. To those who feel that we are going too far in our limitations of the domain accessible to the scientist, I reply: These questions which we forbid you to investigate, and which you so regret, are not only insoluble, they are illusory and devoid of meaning., [11](page 163).

4.2 Hendrik Antoon Lorentz's (1904) seminal article: Electromagnetic Phenomena in a System Moving with Any Velocity Less Than That of Light, [15] (pages 11-34).

In the first page of this article H.A. Lorentz writes: *The problem of determining the influence exerted on electric and optical phenomena by a translation, such as all systems have in virtue of the Earth's annual motion, admits of a comparatively simple solution, so long as only those terms need be taken into*

account, which are proportional to the first power of the ratio between the velocity of translation v and the velocity of light c . Cases in which quantities of the second order, i.e. of the order v^2/c^2 , may be perceptible, present more difficulties. The first example of this kind is Michelson's well-known interference experiment, the negative result of which has led Fitzgerald and myself to the conclusion that the dimensions of solid bodies are slightly altered by their motion through the ether. Some new experiments, in which a second order effect was sought for, have recently been published. Rayleigh and Brace have examined the question whether the Earth's motion may cause a body to become doubly refracting. At first sight this might be expected, if the just mentioned change of dimensions is admitted. Both physicists, however, have obtained a negative result. In the second place Trouton and Noble have endeavoured to detect a turning couple acting on a charged condenser, the plates of which make a certain angle with the direction of translation. The theory of electrons, unless it be modified by some new hypothesis, would undoubtedly require the existence of such a couple.

4.3 Henri Poincaré's (1905) article: Sur la dynamique de l' électron, [9].

Let's see the contents of the first pages of this Poincaré's significant article, written before the appearance of the first edition (1909) of H.A. Lorentz's epoch-making book: The Theory of Electrons, [12].

Poincaré writes: "Il semble au premier abord que l'aberration de la lumière et les phénomènes optiques et électriques qui s'y rattachent vont nous fournir un moyen de déterminer le mouvement absolu de la Terre, ou plutôt son mouvement, non par rapport aux autres astres, mais par rapport à l'éther. Fresnel l'avait déjà tenté, mais il reconnut bientôt que le mouvement de la Terre n'altère pas les lois de la réfraction et de la réflexion... Il semble que cette impossibilité de mettre en évidence expérimentalement le mouvement absolu de la Terre soit une loi générale de la Nature; nous sommes naturellement portés à admettre cette loi, que nous appellerons le Postulat de la Relativité et à l'admettre sans restriction. Que ce Postulat, jusqu'ici d'accord avec l'expérience, doive être confirmé ou infirmé plus tard par des expériences plus précises, il est, en tout cas intéressant de voir quelles en peuvent être les conséquences. Une explication a été proposée par Lorentz et par Fitz Gerald, qui ont introduit l'hypothèse d'une contraction subie par

tous les corps dans le sens du mouvement de la Terre et proportionnelle au carré de l'aberration; cette contraction, que nous appellerons la contraction lorentzienne, rendrait compte de l'expérience de Michelson, et de toutes celles qui ont été réalisées jusqu'ici. L'hypothèse deviendrait insuffisante, toutefois, si l'on voulait admettre dans toute sa généralité le postulat de relativité.

Lorentz a cherché alors à la compléter et à la modifier de façon à la mettre en concordance parfaite avec ce postulat. C'est ce qu'il a réussi à faire dans son article intitulé: *Electromagnetic phenomena in a system moving with any velocity smaller than that of light* (*Proceedings de l'Académie d'Amsterdam*, 27 Mai 1904). L'importance de la question m'a déterminé à la reprendre; les résultats que j'ai obtenus sont d'accord avec ceux de M. Lorentz sur tous les points importants; j'ai été seulement conduit à les modifier et à les compléter dans quelques points de détail; on verra plus loin les différences qui sont d'une importance secondaire.

L'idée de Lorentz peut se résumer ainsi: si l'on peut, sans qu'aucun des phénomènes apparents soit modifié, imprimer à tout le système une translation commune, c'est que les équations d'un milieu électromagnétique ne sont pas altérées par certaines transformations que nous appellerons transformations de Lorentz; deux systèmes, l'un immobile, l'autre en translation, deviennent ainsi l'image exacte l'un de l'autre.

Langevin⁷ avait cherché à modifier l'idée de Lorentz; pour les deux auteurs, l'électron en mouvement prend la forme d'un ellipsoïde aplati, mais pour Lorentz deux des axes de l'ellipsoïde demeurent constants, pour Langevin au contraire c'est le volume de l'ellipsoïde qui demeure constant. Les deux savants ont d'ailleurs montré que ces deux hypothèses s'accordent avec les expériences de Kauffmann, aussi bien que l'hypothèse primitive d'Abraham (électron sphérique indéformable).

L'avantage de la théorie de Langevin, c'est qu'elle ne fait intervenir que les forces électromagnétiques et les forces de liaison; mais elle est incompatible avec le postulat de relativité; c'est que Lorentz avait montré, c'est que je retrouve à mon tour par une autre voie en faisant appel aux principes de la Théorie des Groupes.

Il faut donc en revenir à la théorie de Lorentz; mais si l'on veut la conserver et éviter d'intolérables contradictions, il faut supposer une force

⁷Langevin avait été devancé par M. Bucherer de Bonn, qui a émis avant lui la même idée (voir BUCHERER: *Mathematische Einführung in die Elektronentheorie*, août 1904, Teubner, Leipzig).

spéciale qui explique a la fois la contraction et la constance de deux des axes. J'ai cherché a déterminer cette force, j'ai trouvé qu'elle peut être assimilée a une pression extérieure constante, agissant sur l'électron déformable et compressible, et dont le travail est proportionnel aux variations du volume de cet électron.

Si alors l'inertie de la matiere était exclusivement d'origine électromagnétique, comme l'on admet généralement depuis l'expérience de Kaufmann, et qu'a part cette pression constante dont je viens de parler, toutes les forces soient d'origine électromagnétique, le postulat de relativité peut être établi en toute rigueur. C'est ce que je montre par un calcul tres simple fondé sur le principe de moindre action."

4.4 Louis de Broglie's (1937) article: État actuel de nos connaissances sur la structure de l' Electricité, [6].

In this excellent article de Broglie goes further including Dirac's work. The main points of the article are: *Il n'est pas exagéré de dire que toute la structure de la Matiere nous semble aujourd'hui reposer sur l'existence et les propriétés de cette Electricité, dont les travaux des deux illustres Savants Italiens ont contribué d'une maniere si décisive a nous réveler l'importance. Il est même curieux de noter qu' a l'heure actuelle nous cherchons a déduire presque toutes les propriétés de la Matiere a partir de celles d'une entité physique dont les savants antérieurs au XVIII siecle soupçonnaient a peine l'existence... Nous allons voir que la découverte de corpuscules élémentaires d' électricité, tout en établissant la structure granulaire de l'électricité, a paru confirmer le point de vue de la théorie des deux fluides. Puis, par un mouvement d'oscillation qui s'observe fréquemment au cours de l'histoire des sciences, la récente théorie des "trous" de M. Dirac nous a ramené en un certain sens vers l'idée du fluide unique, mais il se peut que cette théorie se transforme un jour ou l'autre en se rapprochant de l'hypothese dualiste... Plus importante pour le sujet qui nous occupe a été l'apparition, au cours du développement des théories quantiques de l'électron, de la notion de "Spin".*

4.5 Some further remarks.

Let's resume what is included in the four above mentioned fundamental articles by Poincaré ([9], [16]), Lorentz ([12]) and de Broglie ([6]). A bibliography is included for each item.

1. The absolute motion of the Earth.

A rich and well-documented source is Tonnelat's: *Histoire du principe de relativité*, [17].

2. Fresnel's Recognition of the fact that the Earth's motion doesn't change the laws of reflection and refraction.

A valuable help may be found in Bridgman's: *A Sophisticate's Primer of Relativity (2nd edition)*, [13] (pages 29-51).

We may also consider the following Bridgman's remarks: " *What sort of thing is light anyway? To what extent do ordinary concepts apply to it? In particular, does the concept of velocity apply, or that of causality?*

Light, or radiation in general, plays a role at all levels of experience, but the role it plays may be different at different levels. It may be because of this difference of roles that the words of relativity theory and quantum theory are so greatly different from the world of everyday life.

The common-sense world of everyday life is composed of external objects whose relation to us and to each other is continually changing and which constitute our most immediate and vital concern. At this level, the role of radiation is to give us information about these external objects. At this level, the radiation which informs us about an object is without reaction back on the object. This information may be of the most varied sorts, including information about the location of objects and such of their properties as can be inferred from general appearance combined with past experience. These properties include shape and color immediately. The radiation with which we are concerned at this level is entirely in the optical range, and the correspondent phenomena involve the sense of sight. In the realm of the phenomena of sight, it is possible to develop a completely autonomous and independent science of optics, which includes much, but not all, of what is usually understood as geometrical optics and physical optics. The subject of optics which thus arises to deal with the experience of everyday life is sharply separated

from what is understood by mechanics, because in optics such things as forces, masses and velocities do not appear. At the level of naive, first experience, we have no inkling that light has a "velocity" or that a beam of light exerts a pressure. The reason that ordinary experience has no inkling of these things is that our ordinary instruments, including our senses as instruments, are not sensitive enough, since the velocity of light is too high and its pressure is too low for measurement with such tools.", [13] (pages 30,31).

It is, also, instructive to follow Bridgman's thought in the paragraph concerning the *Propagation Aspects of Light* of [13]: *"Relativity theory, as usually presented, visualizes an optical disturbance as initiated at some center and travelling through the surrounding space as an identifiable entity, like a water wave on the surface of a pond. I have emphasized in some of my writings that this method of visualizing the situation assumes more than is necessary. We have no experimental evidence of light as 'a thing traveling', but the light of experience is exhaustively described (except under such abnormal physiological conditions as when we receive a blow on the eyeball) in terms of things lighted. The nature of our entire perceptual world is determined by this fact. We see the "things lighted" as self-contained sources of light, and we are never conscious of the act of reception in our retinas, without which the source would be impotent. We have here the causal asymmetry at a certain level of which we have already been speaking.*

But although our perceptions do not usually directly reveal it to us, there still is something progressive about a beam of light. We can make the path of a beam visible with motes of dust in the beam, and when the beam is turned on we can see the head of the illuminated region progressing, if we are sufficiently far away and at right angles to the path of the beam. Now it would seem to make very little difference for most purposes whether we think of the propagation of light in terms of the progress of the head of an illuminated region or in terms of the motion of some more material thing. My present feeling, therefore, is that the device of conventional relativity theory of thinking of light as a "thing traveling" has been innocent and has led to no false result. However, it is just as easy to think of light propagation in terms of the advance of a lighted region, and I prefer to think in these terms.

It is to be specially noted that all the preceding discussion deals with

light as a macroscopic phenomenon. The intensity of our beams is great enough so that we can siphon off part of it to illuminate the dust motes with no appreciable effect on what is left. When it comes to light of such low intensity that we have only single photons, this conceptual approach loses its validity. Indeed, whether it is proper to think of single photons in terms of "things" is questionable. Special theory, as a whole, is a macroscopic theory. It is rather paradoxical that the present consensus of theoretical physicists seems to be that it is just in the microscopic domain of nuclear phenomena that relativity theory has its most important applications and that we are not most sure of the results.", [13] (pages 39, 40).

Useful remarks are included in Derek Frank Lawden's: *Elements Of Relativity Theory*, [14].

Concerning the Propagation of Light, Lawden writes:*The first law of optics states that light is propagated with the same velocity c in all directions in empty space. As a result of Maxwell's development of the theory of electromagnetism, based upon his system of equations relating the field to the flow of electric charge, it was established that light is an electromagnetic wave, whose electric and magnetic fields are always perpendicular to the direction of propagation, i.e a transverse wave...*

Maxwell conceived electric and magnetic fields as arising when an all pervasive elastic medium, he called the aether, was put into a state of stress. Thus he regarded a light wave as a wave of stress being propagated through the aether in the same way that a sound wave is a wave of compression propagated through the atmosphere. This being the case, assuming the aether is homogeneous and isotropic (i.e. has the same properties in all its parts and in all directions), the velocity of propagation of light wave through it will always be the same, as required by the first law of optics.

Unfortunately, if this model of the physical situation is correct, this optical law cannot be in conformity with the special principle of relativity for it is clear that it will be valid only in a frame at rest in the aether. Relative to any other frame, the aether will be in motion, i.e. an aether wind will blow through the frame, and this will result in the velocity of light being increased in the downwind direction and decreased in the upwind direction. This is certainly the case with sound waves; if the

wind is blowing towards the listener, he will hear the sound of a distant bell sooner than if the wind is blowing away. Successive positions of the wavefront from a point source of light observed from (i) a frame at rest in the aether and (ii) from one in which the aether is in motion, are indicated in Fig.1.3.

To check upon this effect, in 1887 Michelson and Morley in the United States compared the velocity of light in two perpendicular directions, but were unable to detect any difference. It being possible that they had been unfortunate in their timing of the experiment and that the earth happened to have been stationary in the aether when their observations were made, encouraged them to repeat the experiment six months later when the earth was on the other side of its orbit. In spite of the fact that the earth's velocity in the two positions differed by 40 miles/second, a null result was again recorded on the second occasion also. This evidence therefore suggested that the first law of optics was in conformity with the special principle of relativity.

Although, from our contemporary standpoint, this is entirely satisfactory and what was to be expected, since otherwise an absolute standard of rest (namely the aether) would have been established and found, very unexpectedly to reside in the vicinity of our planet, the result created great difficulties for nineteenth-century science. For if the special principle were valid, then a light wavefront observed as a succession of concentric spheres expanding from a point in one inertial frame, had also to appear in the same form when viewed from any other inertial frame moving relative to the first. According to the intuitive ideas regarding the space-time relationships between two such frames extant at the time, this requirement of the special principle could not be satisfied. Not until Einstein (1905) show how it was possible to change these fundamental ideas in such a manner as to remove the inconsistency was this matter resolved and optics brought under the sway of the special principle of relativity.

Once Einstein had succeeded in taking this giant step forward, it was speedily shown by himself and Minkowski that the underlying equations of Maxwell were also in accord with the special principle. Previously, following Maxwell, physicists had believed that these equations were only strictly valid in a frame at rest in the aether and that additional correction terms, involving the velocity of the aether wind, would be needed

in any other frame. That this would imply that the behavior of electrical machinery would change as the earth moved around his orbit and so would be different in summer and winter, seemed to generate no qualms, presumably because the effect was expected to be of negligible magnitude.[14] (pages 12-15).

3. The Postulate of Relativity.

The original articles can be found in [15].

4. The Electromagnetic Origin of Inertia according to Kaufmann's experiments, Abraham's hypothesis and the Ellipsoidal Electron (Lorentz, Bucherer, Langevin).

For an interesting discussion of the (independent of electromagnetic phenomena) concept of *inertia* have a look at Bridgman: *A Sophisticate's Primer of Relativity (2nd edition)*, [13] (pages 76-78). Concerning the electromagnetic origin of Inertia, one can attentively study Tonnelat: *L'éther immobile de Lorentz et la Théorie de l'électron déformable*⁸, in [17] (pages 102-107).

Tonnelat writes that Abraham's Hypothesis is that the velocity of light depends upon the velocity of the reference system with respect to the aether, [17] (page 108).

Needless to say, the reader can find an excellent and challenging modern study of the fields produced by a charged particle in uniform and in accelerated motion in Heald and Marion [22] (pages 271-285).

A modern introductory treatment of the Radiation Pressure is Heald and Marion's [22] (pages 181, 182).

For Radiation Damping look again at Heald and Marion's [22] (pages 367-370).

5. The Lorentz Transformations.

Here, also, Bridgman: *A Sophisticate's Primer of Relativity (2nd edition)*, [13] (pages 6-12), is valuable. Valuable is, also, Tonnelat [17] (pages 110-112).

6. The Principle of Least Action.

⁸Lorentz's aether and the theory of the deformable electron.

7. Dirac's theory, "spin". Tonnelat [17].

5 Resulting Remarks for the Physics teacher.

We are living in a society whose education reveals that the meaning has no significance. Indeed, in nowadays education, the student is faced with a lot of disparate facts but is not educated to understand their meaning. On the other hand we frequently encounter the (nonsense) remark concerning Quantum Mechanics: '*It works!*'. When the student becomes a teacher and tries to teach his pupils he faces (in a tragic manner) the results of such a miseducation.

One solution, applicable only to a personal level, to that fundamental problem could be lifelong self-study!

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